

The Role of Museums, Monuments and Sites to the Development of Cultural Heritage Tourism Entrepreneurship in Tanzania

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ABSTRACT: Museums, Monuments and Sites are currently becoming the hub of business enterprises. Besides the well-known core functions and roles of the Museums, monuments and Sites throughout the world, that includes but not limited to acquisition, conservation, preservation, researches and awareness rising through educational programs and exhibitions, recently the scope and the roles of museums, monuments and sites have been extended to the development of cultural tourism entrepreneurship. Griffin (2002) in the Kenneth Myer Lecture put it clear that the ultimate goal of entrepreneurship in museums must be the enhancement of the visitors' experience of interaction with the authentic object and the increase in understanding and knowledge. In Tanzania for instance business enterprises, corporate institutions, companies, start-up organizations and individual entrepreneurs have been working together with museums, monuments and sites in their ventures to furnish the needs of their companies, visitors and partners. This paper therefore, intends to unearth various ventures, products and opportunities offered as the Cultural tourism entrepreneurship in Tanzania through Museums, Monuments and Sites. Although the predominant applications of entrepreneurship in museums seem to consist in diversifying income, financing through entrepreneurial endeavors, or stepping into business-like activities (Högberg & Jogmark, 2021; Toepler, 2006), being commercial and entrepreneurial does not necessarily mean deviating from the museum's core values. As Brenton and Bouckaert's argue (2021, p.725), "financial entrepreneurial museums are also progressive, ethical, and innovative". Thus, to make this study easier simple random sampling and observation techniques were used as the tools to collect data and analyse them descriptively.

KEY WORDS: Cultural tourism, Entrepreneurship, Museums, Monuments and Sites.

INTRODUCTION

A pragmatic approach was adopted in this study to explore the existing cultural heritage resources in Tanzania and their contribution towards the development of entrepreneurship. Museums, monuments and sites are some areas to focus on simply because they host a large number of cultural tourism visitors and tourism business ventures and stakeholders. Data were collected using documentary reviews and focus group discussions with key actors in the tourism sub-sector. Results indicate that cultural heritage tourism entrepreneurship is positively correlated to business entrepreneurship growth. The paper highlights the importance of museums, monuments and sites to the growth of entrepreneurship in Cultural heritage tourism in Tanzania.

Museums play a variety of roles ranging from preservation of archaeological and historical sites as well as monuments to heritage protection functions, and manage the archaeological heritage of a region or nation. Some museums also give advice on development proposals and undertake fieldwork researches and explorations to acquire collections. Merriman N.(2010) reveals that the most common roles of the museum, however, are the preservation of sites "by record" through the curation of the finds and records made in advance of the destruction of sites through development, and the dissemination of a conservation ethic through public education programs. It is worth noting that museums vary hugely amongst themselves. Some deal with preservation of collections typologically and thematically like Ethnographic museum, Natural history museum, archaeological museum, Village Museum etc. while others deal with preservation of collections of different varieties like Museum and House of Culture, Majimaji Memorial Museum and Arusha Declaration Museum. Besides there are Personalia Museums like Mwalimu J.K. Nyerere Memorial Museum and Dr. Rashid Mfaume Kawawa Memorial Museum. Apart from museums, Historical, archaeological and paleontological sites and monuments play an important role in preservation of heritage assets in Tanzania.

Adela C. and Izabela P. (2012) argue that "even if it is a relatively new concept, entrepreneurship has gone through a thorough analysis both in the commercial and in the social area. As regards social entrepreneurship, it has been noticed that, generally speaking, it is in its turn connected to the private sector, there being few studies which analyze the manner in which entrepreneurship

could be applied to the public sector” Besides the well-known core functions and roles of the Museums, monuments and Sites (MMS) throughout different parts of Tanzania and the world at large, that includes but not limited to acquisition, conservation, preservation, researches and awareness rising through educational programs and exhibitions, this paper therefore, brings out different scope and role of museums, monuments and sites, that has been extended to the development of Cultural Tourism entrepreneurship in the country.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual framework: Cultural Heritage Tourism Entrepreneurship

The term “*Heritage*” in this paper refers to our legacy “inheritance” from the past, what we live with today, and what we pass on to future generations, including the natural and cultural, tangible as well as intangible assets with significance/value (ICOMOS, 1999). The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) define “*tourists*” as people who ‘travel to and stay in places outside their usual environment for more than twenty-four hours and not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes not related to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited (WTTC, 2015).

“*Cultural heritage*” involves aspects of culture that are considered as inheritance and resulting from humanity’s interaction with or intervention in the physical world, including tangible and intangible assets that have cultural significance (Lwoga, 2017). According to Kuratko D.F and Hodgetts R.M (1995) “*an entrepreneur*” means an innovator or developer who recognizes and seizes opportunities, converts those opportunities into workable or marketable ideas, adds value through time, effort, money or skills, assumes the risks of the competitive marketplace to implement these ideas and realize the rewards from these effort. With this understanding therefore, Schumpeter, J.A. (1934) views entrepreneurs as the critical agents for economic change and development while Arthur C. (1946) defined Entrepreneurship as a bridge that makes connection between society and founded institutes for utilizing economic advantages and satisfaction of economic wishes. Tourism entrepreneurship is therefore, defined as activities related to creating and operating a legal tourist's enterprise (Saayman & Saayman, 1998).

A *museum* is a not-for-profit, permanent institution in the service of society that researches, collects, conserves, interprets and exhibits tangible and intangible heritage. Open to the public, accessible and inclusive, museums foster diversity and sustainability. They operate and communicate ethically, professionally and with the participation of communities, offering varied experiences for education, enjoyment, reflection and knowledge sharing (ICOM, 2022). According to the Association of Art Museum Directors “museums, like universities, are intellectual enterprises”. They provide an array of cultural programs and services, including the care, preservation, and conservation of collections, scholarship and library services, youth and adult education, publication, exhibition, public programming and other arts-related activities. Each of these-lines of business is essential to the museum’s fulfilment of its mission (Association of Art Museum Directors, 2001).

It is true that entrepreneurs bring out new products and services to the target population, outline alternative ways for servicing, and new ventures in demand of products so as to satisfy the customers and maximize profit (Angelo, 2017). The development of cultural tourism entrepreneurship as a generator of income and a recognized form of tourism venture has emerged as an objective of both heritage institutions and tourist operators across Tanzania and around the world. The Museums, Galleries, Sites, Information Centres as well as Individual Art galleries and Monuments are among the heritage institutions that have been engaging themselves as the main products or attractions of cultural tourism entrepreneurship in Tanzania. Cultural heritage tourism is a growing segment of tourism all over the world, accounting for about 37% of all tourist trips in the world (WTO, 2015). However, its contribution to the development of the place partly depends on the involvement of community members (entrepreneurs).

Furthermore, in Tanzania for instance, the new tourism policy, which was adopted in 1999, emphasized the promotion of the economy, poverty alleviation, sustainable and quality tourism that is culturally and socially acceptable, ecologically friendly, environmentally sustainable, and economically viable (URT, 1999). In the same year, the monopoly of government operations in tourism business was completely transferred to the private sector through the adoption of the first National Tourism Policy of Tanzania. The policy provided objectives and strategies to achieve sustainable tourism development, and emphasized improvement of private sector participation, and led to the approval of many tourism projects (Anderson, 2014). This paved ways for cultural tourism entrepreneurs to increase new ventures in the sector.

METHODOLOGY

This study applies pragmatic and hermeneutic phenomenology research approaches that involve empirical activities, like collecting experiences, and reflective activities, like analysing their meanings. Data were collected through interviews as this study intends to unearth various ventures, products and opportunities offered as the Cultural tourism entrepreneurship in Tanzania through Museums, Monuments and Sites. Simple random sampling techniques and Qualitative data analysis were applied so as to get precise results that clearly were presented descriptively. Ten (10) respondents including private companies, travel agents and individual tour guides were interviewed at different localities and time. The use of achieves and previous publications was another approach that was used to complement the first hand information obtained from interviews.

INTERVIEW QUESTION: What is the role of Museum, Monuments and Sites to the development of Cultural Heritage tourism Entrepreneurship in Tanzania?

In this study, ten (10) respondents were interviewed based on the benefits obtained from museums, monuments and sites in fostering entrepreneurship growth especially in cultural heritage tourism. Five (5) out of them were private companies, three were Primary and secondary School tour organizers and two (2) were individual registered tour guides. In order to get precise results, an open-ended questionnaire was designed and printed out for them to fill in.

FINDINGS

As noted above, analysis of the data identified a number of roles (significances) that provide insight into how MMS can promote the development of Cultural Heritage Tourism Entrepreneurship in Tanzania. The following are some of the findings obtained from interviews.

The formulation of good policy framework. The government has formulated a good policy framework that allows entrepreneurs to engage themselves in cultural heritage tourism activities. For instance in 1998, the country reviewed the 1991 National Tourism Policy through the Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism. The review was influenced by significant global and national political, economic and social changes such as the rapid development of technology and increased competition in the tourism industry. The new tourism policy, which was adopted in 1999, emphasized the promotion of the economy, poverty alleviation, sustainable and quality tourism that is culturally and socially acceptable, ecologically friendly, environmentally sustainable, and economically viable (URT, 1999). Good policy framework was mentioned by seven respondents out of ten. In connection to this, the cultural heritage tourism programmes are under the stewardship of the Tanzania Tourist Board (TTB) in collaboration with MNRT through the Department of Antiquities and The National Museum of Tanzania.

Improving accessibility: Four out of ten respondents mentioned accessibility as a very important factor. This refers to the ability for tourists to reach the destination. This comprises transportation, which needs to be frequently scheduled, economical, safe and comfortable. The important modes of transportation are road, rail, air and water transport. The Government of United Republic of Tanzania has improved infrastructures around Museums, Monuments and sites for easy accessibility by tourists and entrepreneurs.

Accommodation facilities. This was also mentioned by two tourist companies and two registered individual tour guides. It means tourists have a place to stay and food to eat on reaching at the destination. It can be of two types: Primary accommodations and Secondary accommodations. Primary accommodations include hotels, Resorts, Heritage Hotels etc. and Secondary accommodations include Motels, Youth Hostels, Holiday centres etc. For instance at the Museum and House of Culture, Village Museum and Natural National History Museum, existence of restaurants play a big role in the development of entrepreneurship.

Improvement and refurbishment of attractions. The management of Museums, Monuments and sites have been playing the role of improving both temporary and permanent exhibitions in order to attract more visitors and foster entrepreneurship growth. They ensure that a place visited should have appeal that forces tourist to visit. Two types: Natural attractions and Man-made attractions. Natural attractions include: climate, mountains, beaches etc. and man-made attractions include theme parks, museum, historical monuments etc.

To ensure availability of amenities at tourist destinations is one of the roles of museums, monuments and sites' management. Respondents reported that in Tanzania, the Management of Museums, Monuments and sites ensure the availability of amenities at tourist destinations as these are the basic facilities that every tourist takes for granted and are supposed to be provided for example drinking water, telecommunications, roads, public toilets, banks, mobile banking, etc.

Availability of tourist activities. These are the entertainments available for the tourists in an area. It can also be natural and artificial. Natural activities include sea bathing, possibility of fishing etc. and artificial activities include entertainment parks, water parks etc. Respondents reveal that at the Museum and House of Culture there is “*Museum Arts Explosion program*” that is conducted monthly. The program engages Artistic entrepreneurs to showcase their Artistic works accompanied by stage performances. This program helps a branding package for Artistic works as the same time as an attraction to museum visitors. Furthermore, Mwalimu Nyerere Marathon at Mwalimu Nyerere Memorial Museum, Majimaji Festival at Majimaji Memorial Museum and Kijiji Soko at Village Museum are some of programs that attract many tourists as well as promote cultural heritage tourism entrepreneurial growth in the country.

Employment opportunities. Some respondents revealed that Museums, Monuments and Sites helps in providing employment opportunities to large population covering from skilled to unskilled, as it is a labour intensive industry through strengthening cultural heritage tourism entrepreneurship.

Foreign Exchange: Museums, Monuments and Sites help in Generating foreign exchange for the country as tourism sector is the first largest earner of foreign exchange to Tanzania and fosters income generation to entrepreneurs because it has a wide potential and helps in attracting large number of tourists, therefore it increasing income.

Diversification of the economy. Cultural Heritage Tourism Entrepreneurs can be linked with local products and resources and thus helps in diversifying the economy hence an increase of government revenues: One of the respondents stated that “*it helps in increasing governmental revenues by generating profits*”.

Furthermore, improvement of the standard of living was mentioned by respondents. The Government through Museums, Monuments and Sites in Tanzania through promoting and strengthening Cultural Heritage Tourism Entrepreneurship helps in improving the quality of the life because of the higher level of income and thus leads to improved standards of living.

International peace and cooperation was among of the results: One of the respondents opened that through joint exhibitions in Museums, joint research and co-operations in conservation and preservation of Monuments and sites promote a global community by supporting international understanding and peace all over the world.

DISCUSSION

Cultural heritage tourism entrepreneurship occupies a central place in debates on unlocking the innovative, non-technological potential of MMS taking into consideration the diversity and rich culture of the countries’ history in the respective zone. Thus, entrepreneurial thinking in MMS is unique and cannot be viewed in the same way as a start-up business or new commercial venture in Tanzania. Instead it’s a progressive way of developing commercial strands within the public sector. So one would be encouraged to identify entrepreneurial tourism activity, identify the target audiences (visitors) for whom activities or resources have been developed, and the type of income rose.

In recent decades, a growing trend can be seen in MMS adopting more business strategies and entrepreneurial activities due to a decrease in both governmental subsidies and philanthropic donations against the increase in social and political needs and demands. The combination of these has quietly piloted the concept of social entrepreneurship into the museum world (Eid, 2019), which gives hope with regard to the potential benefits that entrepreneurial initiatives may bring (Murphy, 2018; Surugiu & Surugiu, 2015). Despite not being a widely recognized or identified field, research on the roles of museums, monuments and sites in relation to entrepreneurship studies appears to have the potential to develop into a discussion around the topic of Cultural Heritage tourism entrepreneurship. In light of this, we call for filling this epistemological gap of MMS interacting with entrepreneurship and for highlighting the tensions and paradoxes arising from this interface.

One of the biggest challenges why museums may hold prejudice and precaution when dealing with the infusion of entrepreneurship into their practices has a lot to do with what the concept is commonly known for (Högberg & Jogmark, 2021). Famously developed notably by Schumpeter and Kirzner to the end of maximizing profits through creating, discovering, and exploiting opportunities, entrepreneurship has been widely favored by many economic-focused organizations whilst money seems to run in its blood (Klyver & Bager, 2017). In this connection, Deakins and Freel (2003) argue that some touristic destinations have been revitalized by ethnic minority entrepreneurship, which has increasingly evolved from being solely concentrated in the catering, retailing and clothing industries to being associated with the nascent industrial sectors. It is obvious that the need of understanding the importance of

MMS in developing tourism entrepreneurship and related industries has become an increasingly interesting topic of research and study.

CONCLUSION

Generally, the role of MMS in the development of cultural heritage tourism entrepreneurship can neither be underestimated nor totally ignored. Areas like Bagamoyo Historic Town including Kaore ruins, Caravan Cerai, Ngome Kongwe and Msalabani beach resorts, Mikindani Historic towns, Kilwa kisiwani and Songo Mnara ruins, Majimaji memorial graves, Kunduchi ruins, Askari monuments, Museums and Art galleries have contributed greatly toward the growth of tourism entrepreneurship. Cultural traditions and customs of the people along the coast have emerged the products of tourist as local entrepreneurs tend to buy and sell handcrafts which in turn improve their economic earnings. Furthermore, international co-operation and political atmosphere are being strengthened through joint tourism activities like hotels tour operations as well as adventure activities. Joint research and exhibition in MMS presents a sense of belonging and accruing cultural values. In deed this study brings together socio-political and economic benefits of MMS toward CHTE growth. Finally, Shedding new light on discussions around cultural heritage branding, sponsorship, the politics of display and experience economy, and highlighting the importance of resilience, decolonization and social responsibility, *Museums and Entrepreneurship* is essential reading for students and researchers in museum and heritage studies, curatorial studies, arts and heritage management and business.

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